

Education Quarterly Reviews

Caner, K., & Bahçalı, T. (2022). An Investigation into Lecturers' Perceptions and Experiences Regarding Students with Special Needs. *Education Quarterly Reviews*, 5(1), 209-218.

ISSN 2621-5799

DOI: 10.31014/aior.1993.05.01.432

The online version of this article can be found at:
<https://www.asianinstituteofresearch.org/>

Published by:
The Asian Institute of Research

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An Investigation into Lecturers' Perceptions and Experiences Regarding Students with Special Needs

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Abstract

This study aimed to examine lecturers' perceptions and experiences regarding their students with special needs. The research was designed within the framework of the qualitative research paradigm. The participants of this descriptive study were nine lecturers of two different universities in Turkey who had experience in teaching students with special needs. They were working in different departments/programs such as midwifery, foreign languages, and interior architecture. The students with special needs had different disabilities such as physical disability, hearing impairment, and visual impairment. Data were collected through semi-structured interviews in the fall semester of the 2021-2022 academic year. The data were analyzed via content analysis.

Keywords: Lecturers, Students with Special Needs, Experience

1. Introduction

In Turkey, Regulation for Special Education Services (ÖEHY) is one of the regulations that define individuals with special needs and inform how the educational arrangements related to these students should be. This regulation defines the services to be provided to individuals with special needs as "training programs developed to meet the educational and social needs of individuals who have significant differences from their typical peers in terms of their individual and developmental characteristics and educational qualifications, and training services provided by specially trained personnel in appropriate environments" (Special Education Services Regulation [ÖEHY], 2021). Based on these statements, individuals with special needs develop differently from their typical peers in terms of some characteristics. When these differences are above a certain limit, it may be difficult for them to benefit from standard education programs. That is, these individuals have special needs in line with their special differences. Those with such needs are called individuals with special needs (Akçamete, 2016; Ataman, 2013; Baykoç Dönmez, 2010; Cavkaytar & Diken, 2012; Cavkaytar, 2017; Diken & Batu, 2013).

Individuals with special needs include individuals with mental, hearing, visual as well as physical disabilities. Also, gifted individuals can be considered as individuals with special needs due to their mental differences.

Education offered to individuals with special needs is carried out in two different educational environments. While some individuals with special needs receive separate education in special education schools, some of them are trained together with their typical peers (Kavale, 1979; ÖEHY, 2021). Thus, for individuals with special needs to benefit from general education services together with their typically developing peers, adaptations must be made in education programs and these individuals should be supported (Akçamete, 2016; Diken & Batu, 2013; Ataman, 2013; Baykoç Dönmez, 2010; Cavkaytar & Diken, 2012; Hallahan et al., 2020; ÖEHY, 2021).

Regarding the support to be provided to individuals with special needs, Article 15 of Law No. 5378 on the Disabled states that integrative practices will be included in the general education system so that individuals with special needs can access education at every education level. The same article indicates that “Disabled People Counseling and Coordination Centers” will be established within the universities to ensure the effective participation of university students with special needs in education. The duties of these centers are to provide appropriate equipment and course materials, suitable education, research and accommodation opportunities for individuals with special needs, and to ensure that studies are carried out to solve the problems experienced by these individuals in terms of education (Law No. 5378 on the Disabled).

In Turkey, there are 51,647 university students with special needs according to the data of the Council of Higher Education. While 27,782 of these students are studying an associate degree, 23,581 of them continue to undergraduate programs. Besides, there are 236 students with special needs continuing their graduate programs, and 48 students with special needs are Ph.D. candidates (http1). Meeting the special needs of these individuals and making them benefit from educational services is both a legal obligation and a requirement (Law on the Disabled No. 5378; Ataman, 2013; Kargın, 2004; Kavale, 1979; ÖEHY, 2021).

In Turkey, there is a limited number of studies examining the state of individuals with special needs who continue their associate degree, bachelor’s degree, and/or doctoral degree and determining the experiences and needs of the academicians who teach these students. Güray (2014) aimed to identify the experiences of a graduate student with visual impairment during the education process and thus to offer suggestions to the lecturers. Some of the suggestions were that the lecturers make presentations more slowly, provide psychological and technical support to students with special needs, ensure that students sit at the front of the class, prepare easily accessible and simple course materials, and give students with special needs more time to prepare homework. Yalçın and Aslan (2021) examined the difficulties experienced by academicians teaching university students with visual impairment. They reported that academicians had problems in preparing and adapting content for students with special needs. The available research has mostly focused on students with visual impairment and the lecturers teaching these students. However, as stated in the relevant statistics of the Council of Higher Education, around 50,000 individuals with special needs are university students. These individuals have different special needs such as hearing impairment, visual impairment, physical disability (http1). Therefore, it is important to conduct similar studies in a wider scope and cover different special needs groups. In this sense, examining the perceptions and experiences of lecturers regarding individuals with special needs is necessary to close this gap in the literature. This study aimed to examine lecturers’ perceptions and experiences regarding their students with special needs in their classes and to reveal the difficulties and deficiencies the lecturers experienced. To achieve this goal, the following research questions were asked:

- a) What are the perceptions of lecturers teaching individuals with special needs about these individuals?
- b) What are the experiences of lecturers when teaching individuals with special needs?

2. Method

This research aimed to investigate the perceptions and experiences of the lecturers who teach individuals with special needs. The study was designed as descriptive research within the framework of the qualitative research paradigm. Adopting data collection techniques such as interviews, observations and document analysis, qualitative research aims to present the current situation and the phenomenon realistically and holistically. Qualitative research is not concerned with generalization. The qualitative data should be examined according to the conditions they are in (Cresswell, 2016; Mills & Gay, 2016; Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2018). In this research, qualitative data were

collected from lecturers working in three universities in two different cities in the Central Anatolian Region of Turkey.

2.1 Participants

Data were collected from lecturers working in three universities in the Central Anatolian Region of Turkey. To ensure participant confidentiality, code names were used.

Table 1: Demographic Information of Lecturers

Code Number	Code Name	Age/Gender	Department/program	Professional Experience (years)	Special Needs Type of Student(s)	Number of Students with Special Needs
1.	Melek	50/F	Psychological counseling and guidance	24	Visual impairment	1
2.	Kadir	32/M	Basic Islamic sciences	7	Visual impairment, physical disability	3
3.	Özgür	37/F	Turkish language and literature	12	Visual impairment, physical disability	5
4.	Halil	45/M	Translation and interpreting	12	Visual impairment	1
5.	Adil	35/M	Education management	9	Visual impairment	2
6.	Kerem	43/M	Midwifery	20	Hearing impairment, physical disability	2
7.	Meryem	48/F	Philosophy	24	Autism spectrum disorder, Visual impairment	3
8.	Berke	32/M	Interior architecture	9	Physical disability	1
9.	Burak	52/M	Measurement and evaluation	17	Visual impairment	1

Not: K=Kadın, E=Erkek

2.2 Data Collection and Analysis

Semi-structured interview questions were created by the authors. These questions were sent to four experts on special education and qualitative research methods. Then, the authors came together and discussed expert opinions. Based on the expert opinions, questions were finalized (see Table 2).

Table 2: Semi-Structured Interview Questions

1. What do special needs mean to you? What do you know about students with special needs?
2. What did you experience when you met your student with special needs for the first time?
3. When you met your student with special needs for the first time, what did you know about your student's needs?
4. What methods did you do to learn about the needs of your student with special needs?
5. Did you make any change(s) in the teaching and evaluation processes for students with special needs? What is(are) the changes(s)? What changes did you make during face-to-face and/or online education?

6. What were the activities that you easily did for your students with special needs during the teaching and evaluation process?
 7. In which subject(s) did you have difficulties with your students with special needs during the teaching and evaluation process? Can you give examples?
 8. What kind of gains do you think a student with special needs has provided for you? Do you have anything negative to say about it? (For example, caring is tiring, it is time-consuming)
 9. Do you want to be a teacher in a classroom having students with special needs in the future? Why/why not?
 10. What are your suggestions for the arrangements to be made while students with special needs are studying with their typical peers at university?
 11. Is there any other opinion you would like to add on the subject?
-

Data were collected through the interview questions. Semi-structured interviews were conducted between 11.01.2022 and 21.01.2022 by both authors at three different universities in the Central Anatolian Region of Turkey. Demographic information of participants was given in Table 1. Before the interviews were conducted, legal permission was obtained from the scientific research and publication ethics committee of the university where the first author was working.

To recruit the participants, students with special needs studying at the university were reached through the Disabled Student Units of the universities where the authors were working. Then, the students were asked about the courses they took as well as their lecturers. The accessible lecturers were informed about the research. The volunteers were included in the study. Interviews were held on the agreed days and times. Before the interviews, the instructors were informed about the research, data collection processes, and confidentiality. Finally, written and verbal permissions were obtained.

Semi-structured interviews were audio-recorded. Next, the authors transcribed the audio recordings. Then, the transcripts of both authors were checked for accuracy. Thus, the reliability of the interview transcripts was ensured.

During the data analysis, both authors independently read the transcripts three times to ensure that the authors dominate the interview transcripts. The authors adopted content analysis to analyze the data. In the content analysis approach, the data is read and coded by the researcher/s. Then, sub-themes and themes were created through the codes. Besides, direct quotations were included in the content analysis to reflect the views of the participants in the analysis (Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2018). Both authors created themes, sub-themes, and codes independently. The authors created a list of codes, sub-themes and themes. Finally, the authors discussed their analyzes and agreed on the themes, sub-themes, and codes (see Table 3).

3. Results

This study aimed to examine the perceptions and experiences of the lecturers regarding their students with special needs. The data were collected through semi-structured interviews in the fall semester of the 2021-2022 academic year, as explained in the title of "Data Collection and Analysis." The interviews lasted a total of 3 hours, 36 minutes, and 34 seconds. The longest interview was with Adil (35 minutes and 43 seconds). The shortest interview was with Melek (16 minutes and 6 seconds). The average interview time was calculated as 24 minutes, 6 seconds. The transcripts were determined as 87 pages in total.

The themes, sub-themes and codes are given in Table 3. As can be seen in Table 3, two themes were reached: a) lecturers' knowledge and thoughts about individuals with special needs, and b) lecturers' experiences with their students with special needs. Also, 10 sub-themes and 46 codes were reached. The themes, sub-themes and codes were as presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Themes, sub-themes and codes

-
1. Lecturers' knowledge and thoughts about individuals with special needs
 - 1.1. Lecturers' current knowledge about individuals with special needs
 - 1.1.1. Individuals outside the norm

- 1.1.2. Individuals who need others' support
 - 1.1.3. Individuals with disabilities
 - 1.1.4. Individuals who need special support
- 1.2. Lecturers' knowledge of students with special needs regarding their first interaction
 - 1.2.1. Lack of knowledge
 - 1.2.2. Knowing the type of disability of the student with special needs
 - 1.2.3. Adaptations for students with special needs
- 1.3. Lecturers' obtaining information about individuals with special needs
 - 1.3.1. Not getting information
 - 1.3.2. Searching on the internet
 - 1.3.3. Following scientific articles
 - 1.3.4. Asking the student
 - 1.3.5. Getting information from academics
- 1.4. Benefits of teaching students with special needs
 - 1.4.1. Changing their perspectives towards students with special needs
 - 1.4.2. Being thankful for themselves
 - 1.4.3. Motivate themselves to work
 - 1.4.4. Gaining experience
- 1.5. Negative effects of teaching students with special needs
 - 1.5.1. Becoming pessimistic
 - 1.5.2. Low motivation due to student's being late to class
 - 1.5.3. Feeling inadequate
 - 1.5.4. Distraction
 - 1.5.5. Feeling in control due to audio recording
- 1.6. Lecturers' thoughts on teaching students with special needs in the future
 - 1.6.1. Positive
 - 1.6.2. Negative
 - 1.6.3. Depends on the type of special needs
- 1.7. Lecturers' suggestions for students with special needs
 - 1.7.1. Informing lecturers about students with special needs
 - 1.7.2. Providing peer/counselor coaching to students with special needs
 - 1.7.3. Preparing teaching materials according to the needs of students with special needs
 - 1.7.4. Establishing places that will enable students with special needs to socialize
 - 1.7.5. Integrating students with special needs with their peers
 - 1.7.6. Making more use of technology
 - 1.7.7. Improving transportation
 - 1.7.8. Creating places in line with universal design principles
2. Lecturers' experiences with their students with special needs
 - 2.1. Lecturers' adaptations for students with special needs in their courses
 - 2.1.1. Allowing audio recording
 - 2.1.2. Describing the topic verbally
 - 2.1.3. Visualizing the topic
 - 2.1.4. Not adapting
 - 2.1.5. Providing exam/training in a separate environment
 - 2.1.6. Exemption from certain courses
 - 2.1.7. Changing the font size
 - 2.1.8. Changing a student's place in the classroom
 - 2.1.9. Conducting individual lessons online
 - 2.2. Issues that lecturers have difficulty with
 - 2.2.1. Describing the topic verbally
 - 2.2.2. increased workload
 - 2.2.3. Not adapting
 - 2.3. Issues that lecturers find easy

2.3.1. Active participation of the student in the lesson

2.3.2. Contacting the student's family

The lecturers were asked to explain the meaning of “special needs and students with special needs.” Melek, Adil and Kerem defined people with special needs as individuals outside the norm. For example, Melek said, *“For me, these expressions refer to students who are not within the norm. Of course, gifted people are also people who fall outside the norm. But with these concepts, I perceive not the gifted but rather those who are different from the average individuals. For example, students with visual, hearing, and physical disabilities are the first examples that come to mind... Of course, we can add those with chronic health problems to a certain extent.”* Kadir, Özgür, Meryem and Berke stated that individuals with special needs were those needing someone else. For instance, Kadir said, *“Obviously, I think individuals with special needs are people who cannot come here by their own means and cannot normally come like their other friends.”* Halil and Berke also stated that individuals with special needs were those with disabilities. For example, Halil voiced, *“In my opinion, people with special needs are individuals with disabilities such as physical inadequacy and visual impairment.”* Moreover, according to Burak, individuals with special needs were those needing special support: *“Students with special needs remind me that we need to prepare a special effort for them. Special pedagogical approaches and special education programs should be prepared for them. Because these individuals are the ones who need special support.”*

Regarding lecturers’ knowledge about individuals with special needs when they met them for the first time, Melek, Kadir, Adil and Meryem had no information. Adil expressed, *“I didn't know anything. It could not receive training on that subject.”* Özgür and Kerem only knew the disability types. Özgür said: *“So I had at least some prior knowledge. For example, in that class, this student has this disability... At least I knew something about the types of students' disabilities.”* On the other hand, some lecturers (e.g., Halil and Kerem) said that they knew adaptations for students with special needs. Kerem said, *“I was quite relaxed as I could present the lesson visually for the hearing impaired.”*

Participants were asked to explain how they could get information about individuals with special needs. Melek, Kadir, Adil, Kerem, Meryem and Berke did not obtain information during this process. For example, Melek said, *“I did not do anything to gain information for this student.”* Özgür and Halil searched on the internet to be informed about individuals with special needs. For instance, Halil said, *“I followed websites for information a bit.”* Besides, Halil followed scientific articles. Meryem was asking questions to students to get information. she stated, *“I asked them how they study. I tried to understand them so that I could learn something about them...”*. Burak got information thanks to academicians in the field of special education: *“I was thinking about how I could prepare a better educational environment for them. I talked to one of my university professors about this issue. I asked questions about how to decide for the visually impaired. Thankfully, with his help, I managed.”*

Lecturers were asked whether teaching individuals with special needs had positive effects on them. According to Melek, Kadir and Berke, this experience changed their perspectives on these individuals. For example, Berke said, *“It had positive effects. When I saw that they could adapt to life and get used to any environment, my perspective towards them changed positively.”* Kadir and Özgür said that a sense of gratitude is the positive effect of working with individuals with special needs. For example, Kadir voiced, *“When a person sees someone weaker than himself, he is grateful for himself.”* Kerem said that working with individuals with special needs motivated him to work: *“I think the person develops himself/herself. To be able to teach a student with disabilities and to feel competent about that subject, the person feels motivated to work.”* Meryem said that teaching individuals with special needs gave her experience in this regard.

For the negative effects of teaching students with special needs, Kadir said that teaching students with special needs made him pessimistic: *“Sometimes, when you see these friends, you become pessimistic...”* Kerem also stated that he had a loss of motivation towards teaching because of students being late to classes. In addition, Kerem expressed that he felt inadequate due to teaching these students. On the other hand, students with special needs distract Meryem who said, *“From my point of view, I would say that because I am a social scientist, it is a distraction for students.”* Finally, Özgür stated that although he accepted the lesson being recorded, he felt under control because of the voice recording

Regarding whether they would like to teach individuals with special needs in the future, Melek, Meryem, Berke and Burak were optimists. For example, Berke said, *“First of all, I would like to teach them in the future, professionally.”* However, Özgür and Kerem stated that they do not want to teach students with special needs again in the future. For instance, Özgür voiced, *“My field is Turkish Folk Literature. As the name speaks, we must be with people. We must have talks. We need to get records. We should do oral culture and oral history studies. In my field, it is difficult to work with someone who has any disabilities. If we have a student with a disability in graduate education, what can we work with? Frankly, I do not prefer it, especially in folk literature, because it would not be productive.”* Kadir also said that the subject of teaching those individuals changes depending on the types of special needs of the students: *“Some of the individuals with special needs can be more advantageous than others. For example, we cannot explain some concepts to a deaf student because our course is philosophical or intellectual. As far as I know, their conceptual framework is narrower than that of the visually impaired. In addition, I think a visually impaired person can be more advantageous in learning some things than a person with a hearing impairment. For example, we can teach someone visually impaired, but it would probably be difficult for us to teach someone who is hearing impaired. Because it is necessary to learn sign language.”*

The lecturers were asked to mention their suggestions regarding the arrangements for students with special needs studying at the university with their typical peers. According to Melek, Özgür, Adil, Kerem and Burak, lecturers should be informed about individuals with special needs and the education to be given to them. Kerem said, *“Obviously, I don't know anything. However, if you lead the way, I would like to participate in the training you will give. I think all lecturers should be informed about this issue.”* Melek, Adil, Kerem and Berke suggested peer or counselor coaching. Berke said, *“I think it is very important to have a staff member who will help them not only in the rectorate but also in the faculties. This person may also be academic staff.”* Lecturers (Kadir, Özgür and Halil) also advocated that appropriate teaching materials should be prepared for students with special needs. For example, Özgür stated, *“We need smart boards. That's why the teacher has to use his voice all the time. He uses slides, and he says, look, as you can see on the slide, but this has no value for students, so we are very lacking in the use of smart boards and similar technical infrastructures.”* Melek and Burak argued that students with special needs should be integrated with their peers. For example, Melek voiced, *“If I have the file of the student with special needs, I will do my best to integrate them with their peers. Individuals with special needs should already be integrated with their peers.”* Similarly, Meryem stated that places that could serve students with special needs to socialize with their peers should be established. According to Kadir, technology should be used more while teaching students with special needs. Halil suggested that the transportation of individuals with special needs should be improved, and Berke stated that places should be designed in line with universal design principles.

Another theme was lecturers' experiences with their students with special needs. Lecturers explained the adaptations they made in their lessons for their students. Özgür, Adil, Kerem, Meryem and Burak taught their students with special needs in or taking the exam, in a separate environment. For example, Burak said, *“Under normal circumstances, it is not right for a student to support another student in the exam. However, a friend of our students with special needs read the questions in another environment and supported him in the exam.”* Some lecturers (Melek, Adil and Meryem) stated that they allowed audio recordings in the course so that students with special needs could follow the lessons. Adil reported this situation by saying, *“I allowed the audio recording, for example, in my class.”* Melek and Kerem used narration in their classes. Halil and Burak increased the font size in the exams. However, Kadir, Meryem and Burak did not make any adaptations in their lessons. For example, Kadir said, *“I didn't think of making any adaptations, frankly.”* Kerem explained the topics with visuals, and Özgür exempted students with special needs from some courses. Burak also taught some online lessons individually with students with special needs and placed these students in the front row in the lessons he was teaching face to face.

Regarding the issues the lecturers had difficulty in teaching students with special needs, Kadir and Özgür thought that teaching students with special needs increased their workload. For example, Özgür said, *“We are preparing special notes for them. You also spend more time preparing for classes. This increases our workload.”* Melek said that she had difficulty in explaining the subject aloud to them. Adil also had difficulties in designing the lessons for students with special needs.

For the issues they found easier when teaching individuals with special needs, they said that these students could participate actively in lessons, which made things easier for them. For example, Adil said, “*The student works hard. He tries to get as high grades as possible. This is very positive for me.*” Finally, Meryem stated that contacting the student's family was easy for her.

4. Discussion

This study aimed to examine lecturers' perceptions and experiences regarding their students with special needs in their classes. Face-to-face interviews were conducted with the lecturers working in different faculties in two different state universities in Turkey. Based on the interview data, themes were created. It is expected that the research will guide the lecturers who will teach students with special needs at universities, higher education administrators who can make legal arrangements, and researchers.

Regarding lecturers' knowledge of their students with special needs when they met them for the first time, most of the lecturers did not know anything about these students. Two lecturers stated that they knew the types of disabilities of these individuals. Lecturers learned from their students whether there were students with special needs in their classrooms. At this point, it can be said that lecturers are not informed about students with special needs. This situation may affect the quality of education to be given to these students. Therefore, after students with special needs choose their courses, it would be appropriate to inform the lecturers the students with special needs in their classes, the types of disabilities, and what needs to be done.

Lecturers were asked to mention how they got information about students with special needs. Most of them were lack of information. However, some lecturers were found to search on the internet, read scientific publications, get information from academicians who are experts in the field, and get information from the students. There is no doubt that the students with special needs receive a good education thanks to the lecturers who know the characteristics of these individuals well. However, it can be said that some of the lecturers had a lack of knowledge on this subject and they did not have any attempts to make up for this deficiency.

Lecturers were asked about the benefits of teaching students with special needs. Most of the lecturers stated that teaching these students changed their perspectives about students with special needs. However, some lecturers expressed their gratitude for themselves. These findings indicate that students with special needs can be successful at universities when they are given opportunities. Also, findings eliminate the prejudice that students with special needs cannot do anything.

Regarding lecturers' opinions regarding teaching a student with special needs in the future, most of them had positive opinions. Although the lecturers did not have enough knowledge about how to teach a student with special needs, they were optimists about teaching them. Considering the contributions of students with special needs to lecturers, the answers were being grateful for themselves, motivating themselves to work, and gaining experience. Although the lecturers may need to make some adjustments (such as making some adjustments, preparing separate exam questions, and conducting exams in a different environment) while teaching students with special needs, it is pleasing that they have positive attitudes towards teaching students with special needs. Besides, it is common for lecturers to have difficulties or problems in providing education and making arrangements in education, as they have little or no encounter with individuals with disabilities before (Yalçın & Aslan, 2021).

Lecturers stated that they did not have any difficulties in taking exams and preparing questions for these individuals. However, according to Yalçın and Aslan (2021), lecturers teaching visually impaired individuals had difficulties in preparing exams, making exam papers suitable, making exams, and getting reader-writer support in the exam. In a study conducted by Kamaş and Demir (2018), the fact that individuals with visual impairments asked for help in exams was considered a problem.

At the end of the research, lecturers were observed to have various difficulties while teaching individuals with special needs, such as the increase in the workload, making adaptations, and teaching the subject verbally.

Similarly, Yalçın and Aslan (2021) argued that instructors had difficulties in making adaptations for their visually impaired students and in using narration for visual content.

Regarding their suggestions for students with special needs, most of the lecturers wanted to be informed about students with special needs. Because many academics naturally did not know anything about students with special needs, their characteristics, education, and possible adaptations. This might be because they were experts in different fields and lack of training in the field of special education. Similarly, Yalçın and Aslan (2021) suggested training for lecturers teaching individuals with visual impairment. In today's education system, students with different academic, social and physical characteristics receive education in separate classes, but the learning needs of all students with these different learning characteristics must be met (Güray, 2014).

Lecturers did not have information about students with special needs. However, the lecturers stated that they should be given training on students with special needs as a suggestion. Similarly, Güray (2014) recommended training for lecturers regarding students with special needs. Similarly, Kamış and Demir (2018) argued that lecturers teaching individuals with visual impairment did not have information about these students.

Sucuoğlu and Kargın (2006) underlined the importance of socialization of students with special needs and typically developing individuals when they were studying together. According to the findings of this research, lecturers also emphasized the importance of the socialization of these students with their typically developing peers while studying together.

Lecturers insisted on the necessity of using technology, especially when teaching students with special needs. Besides, they believed that the use of technology would facilitate both teaching and learning. Similarly, Güray (2014) recommended the use of technology in education for students with visual impairments and special needs. Güray (2014) suggested that institutions should be aware of their students with visual impairment and that institutions should keep records for these individuals. Also, it is recommended that institutions give information to educators about the visually impaired individual in advance. According to the findings of this research, the lecturers wanted the institutions to inform them about the students with special needs, their inadequacies, and what needs to be done.

Today, some universities offer "Disabled Student Unit" for students with special needs. However, some of the lecturers teaching students with special needs are not aware of these units. Thus, it can be suggested that the activities of such units for students with special needs and the awareness of such units should be increased, and they should cooperate more with the instructors. Future studies may examine the views of university students with special needs studying at different faculties.

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